

ELIMINATION OF MISSIONARY ACTIVITY IN THE STRATEGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW UZBEKISTAN AND ITS FUTURE TASKS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, one of the important priority tasks of our reforms aimed at radically renewing the life of the state and society in our country today is to educate and bring up a mature and harmonious generation in all respects. Namely, today, in the context of the reforms being carried out in our country in the religious-educational, socio-political spheres, one can deeply understand that our people are boldly taking steps towards such noble ideas.

Keywords: Development of Uzbekistan, science, education and religious-educational spheres, law on freedom of conscience and religious organizations.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda davlat va jamiyat hayotini tubdan yangilashga qaratilgan islohotlarimizning muhim ustuvor vazifalaridan biri har tomonla etuk barkamol avlodni tarbiyalash va voyaga etkazishni taqoza etmoqda. Aynan, bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda diniy-ma'rifiy ijtimoiy-siyosiy sohalarda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar zahirida xalqimizni mana shunday ezgu g'oyalar sari dadil odimlayotganligini teran anglash mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbekiston taraqqiyoti, ilm-fan, ta'lim-tarbiya va diniy-ma'rifiy sohalari, vijdon erkinligi va diniy tashkilotlar to'g'risidagi qonun.

Today, one of the important priority tasks of our reforms aimed at radically renewing the life of the state and society in our country requires the upbringing and education of a mature and harmonious generation in all respects. It is precisely in the context of the reforms being implemented in our country today in the religious-educational, socio-political spheres that one can deeply understand that our people are

boldly taking steps towards such noble ideas. In particular, based on the idea of "From national revival to national upsurge", Uzbekistan has entered a new era of development, and the large-scale reforms being implemented in the socio-economic and spiritual-educational spheres are, first of all, creating the basis for the development of our country. As a result of the reforms implemented in the fields of science, education, upbringing and religious-educational spheres in our country, major changes are becoming a great national goal, a nationwide movement.

Today, the rapid reforms being carried out in our country are drawing the world's attention to our homeland with their scale, intensity and wide scope. The fact that the world community is referring to our country with the phrase "New Uzbekistan" when talking about the reforms being carried out under the leadership of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev is certainly a worthy assessment of the changes in our country. In the words of the head of our state, "New Uzbekistan is a time when the noble idea of "The interests of the people are above all else" is being confirmed by practical work." Of course, large-scale reforms and innovations in our country are being implemented on the basis of this humane idea. Today, New Uzbekistan is recognized in the world arena as a country with strong potential, worthy reputation, and a prosperous and prosperous country in all respects, and its influence is growing. The democratic reforms being implemented in our country to ensure that every person lives a happy life are bringing joy to the hearts of our compatriots. Today, the necessary conditions have been created in our country to ensure human dignity, freedom, happiness, and equality, and to realize all the principles of humanity. This is a practical expression of the principle "The State is for the people." After all, serving the people and their happiness, and the interests of the people, is considered the main criterion of humanity. The full realization of the noble principle "For the dignity of the person" in our country, ensuring the rule of law and the Constitution, and the peaceful and safe life of every citizen constitute the fundamental essence of the reforms being implemented and are of great importance in the policy of our state.

In order to continue such reforms in the next five years and ensure their coherence, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan was developed on the basis of the principle of "From a Strategy of Actions to a Strategy of Development". In the V direction of this strategy, entitled "Ensuring Spiritual Development and Bringing the Industry to a New Level", a number of tasks have been defined as the main goal. The

71st goal of the tasks set in this direction is “To transform a healthy worldview and creativity into a nationwide movement in society by widely promoting the idea of “From a Strategy of Actions to a Strategy of Development” based on the principles of goodness and humanity.

It is especially noteworthy that the high attention paid in our country to education, science, culture and enlightenment, and the study and appreciation of the heritage of our ancestors is highly recognized not only by the population of our country and the region, but also by the world community. If we pay attention to the studies and information analysis conducted in this area, we must deeply understand that the activities of "certain" religious organizations that are using the reforms in the religious sphere that have been implemented in our country for their own selfish interests are a violation of our long-established religious values.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Freedom of Conscience and Religious Organizations” No. O’RQ-699 of July 5, 2021, “It is not allowed to use religion for the purpose of forcibly changing the constitutional system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, undermining its sovereignty and territorial integrity, violating the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens, promoting war, national, racial, ethnic or religious hatred, encroaching on the health and morals of citizens, violating the harmony of citizens, spreading slanderous fabrications that destabilize the situation, inciting confusion among the population, and committing other actions directed against the individual, society and the state.”

Currently, modern information technologies and communication tools, under the influence of politicized power centers with large investments, operating in various regions and territories of the world, are consciously "targeting" certain regions and countries and trying to weaken the existing legitimate government by sowing discord between the existing political regime and citizens. Experts note that positive results are being achieved as a result of promoting missionary activities through radio and television. By the way, among the totalitarian sects that are most actively and extensively promoting missionary work and Christianity through radio and television, it is worth mentioning the "Full Gospel Christians" and the "Adventists" sect. Today, missionary programs are broadcast directly on the Russian TV channel in the CIS countries, such as the "Voice of Faith" program of the "Kenneth Copeland Mission", the "Voice of Faith" of the "Joyce Meyer" mission, "SNL", "LIFE TV", "TNB". In

particular, the future plans of the Golos And radio station focus on spreading missionary ideas to the entire world population through radio waves in order to widely promote Christianity. This radio station is currently trying to establish branches in Eastern Europe, Ukraine, Russia, and Central Asia. Through this radio station, it is listening to the Gospel of Jesus, providing medical services, and conveying the ideas of Christian teachings to people.

Through its programs, this radio station, in cooperation with the radio station "Novaya Zhizn-Yangi Hayot" operating in the CIS and Russia, offers its listeners 24 hours a day to enjoy missionary and Christian teachings. In essence, the implementation of the information mission by missionary organizations is primarily aimed at ideological influence by conquering the minds and hearts of people. This situation means that due to the threat to the stability of states, the historically formed values of the nation, its identity, and its existence as a nation and people are at risk. After all, missionary work is aimed at the human heart and mind, and by influencing the socio-spiritual environment of society, it seeks to deprive the nation and people of their national-spiritual roots. Thus, as a result of the change in the beliefs of people influenced by missionary work, they become spiritually subordinate by becoming entangled in a whirlpool of religious feelings and spiritual despair.

According to the results of the analysis of the religious segment of the Internet, religious web portals have the following blocks: news, information on the basics of religious doctrine, sermons in MR3 format, the Bible, testimonies, photo exhibitions, articles, book texts, conferences, announcements, greeting cards, holidays, Christian shops.

Also, religious sites of most currents engaged in missionary work have created conditions for communication for their adherents in the form of guest books, blogs, forums. All this is one aspect of the activity in this area, aimed at the promotion of missionary politics and religion. On the other hand, on the initiative of missionaries, portals have been created on many sites on the Internet that distort the cultural life of a particular region as hotbeds of immorality, murder, backwardness, and evil, which play the role of important factors in discrediting the policies of this country both in internal and external life. ...The reasons for the popularity of the Internet are easy access to communication, ensuring anonymous communication, distributing information worldwide, high speed of information transmission, multimedia capabilities, etc.

At the same time, on social sites where missionary activities are carried out, one can find online conversations, mentoring and training courses, as well as missionary advice, lessons, and healing prayers. Thus, it should be noted that religious sites contain video series, audio sermons, radio, and TV programs. It is especially worth noting that the "Christian Portal" and "Internet Church" are operating on a large scale. The price of topics in the "What does the Bible say" category on these portals is quite high.

As the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, noted: "The organizers of information attacks, pursuing their ideological and selfish interests, are trying to mislead the forces and people who are uniting in the fight against terrorism, the scourge of the 21st century, to cause discord among them, and to instill suspicion in each other." Indeed, one of the features of information attacks is that, first of all, by destroying the historically formed culture, values, and identity of the nation, they create a basis for people to live as a nation and people.

According to information analytical studies, in January 2022, the total number of social media users worldwide reached 4.62 billion people, which is 58.4% of the world's population.

Today's globalization is rapidly increasing, and the impact of the Internet and social networks on people's daily lives is increasing worldwide. This, in turn, creates a basis for missionaries to promote their ideas online through social networks by creating "favorable" conditions. Missionaries who use this effectively and skillfully on social networks easily trap their prey by expanding their hearts and minds. Thus, it is not difficult to understand that the promotion of missionary ideas through social networks is becoming a global threat to humanity on a global scale.

The worrying aspect is that today most of the youth are becoming addicted to social networks. At the same time, according to the results of the conducted studies, the negative impact of the Internet and computers on the human psyche, health and spirituality is becoming increasingly widespread. As a result, the existence of certain diseases, namely "infectious Internet addiction", is being noted as a result of the addiction of young people to the Internet and social networks. This disease is contagious like gambling, isolating a person from his surroundings and social life.

Considering that most of today's youth turn to the Internet as their main source of information, the danger of "electronic traps" is increasing. It should be noted that, as we strive to ensure spiritual security in our country, we need to pay serious attention to the

threats of "digital evangelism" manifested through the Internet and social networks and take necessary measures. After all, it is necessary to understand that missionary manipulation, which is actively operating on the Internet and social networks today, is becoming increasingly powerful and poses a serious threat to the mentality of our nation and people. As is known from history, the range of methods used in the processes of integration and acculturation, which are civilized and cultural, is very wide: countries that are rapidly developing and increasing their influence through modern technologies are also widely using methods of spiritual expansion.

Although the historical picture has changed, the complexity of this problem has not lost its relevance today. In this regard, a comprehensive analysis of the missionary activities of interested countries that have come to another country to expand their influence, affecting the spiritual consciousness, is a requirement of today. World events prove that religion is a great force in the sustainable development of the nation. Therefore, in order to prevent the hidden use of religion, it is necessary not to ignore the missionary threat of unfamiliar organizations against the historically formed values of the Uzbek people.

It is true that a number of new religious associations are operating in our country. Of course, this situation cannot be ignored, and it cannot be denied that some religious organizations that have not been registered since the adoption of the new law on religion are still operating secretly. In order to take measures against them, it is necessary to have a deep understanding of the methods of work of these religious organizations, work technology, indicators for objectively assessing the specific features of missionary activity. In order to analyze the activities of religious movements in our country from the point of view of spiritual processes and technologies, it is important to study their missionary experience, laws and new directions of missionary activity methods. In building a legal democratic civil society, it is important to protect our great spirituality, our holy religion, first of all, from various destructive ideas based on democratic principles. The basis of missionary activity is the connection between mission and culture, the continuity of mission and creativity. It is known that any society lives within a certain culture. Neither Christianity nor the Bible can exist without a literary language. At the heart of missionary activity is the instillation of cultural values into people through religion. In this regard, let us pay attention to the results of the following sociological survey.

The question of what methods do missionaries use to control the minds of their members? The following answer was given:

To the question of what negative impact does missionary activity have on the future of the nation? 67% of respondents indicated that it distances the nation from its religious values, 59% that it undermines the national mentality and the future of the nation, 52% that it creates interfaith conflicts, and 46% that it creates division in the life of society. Such aspects

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